

**THE STORY OF SAID AKROMKHAN'S LAST NAVROZ CELEBRATION
OF HUZOR TORASH (OR ABOUT THE NAVROZ ELECTION, THE
NEW HOME OF THE ORIGINAL THE STORTURKS OF THE
FORGOTTEN KAVCHIN ELI CHOGURTMA PEOPLE.)**

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Annotation. The nationwide project "Green Place" announced in our country is very important. Practical work in this regard is being actively carried out under the initiative of the Honorary Public Council of the Chugurtma Mahalla People's Assembly of Ghuzar District. In particular, the ancient Khuzor (now Guzor) Chinese pearl mulberry trees in the yard of Khojabash father's shrine are the center of attention of many people.

According to the traditions of the ancient Turkic peoples, Navrozi Olam (sayil) holiday came to the borders of the Guzor district of the Bukhara emirate (Sayid Akromkhan led the district from the Boshadi fortress of the Yakkabog district due to the unstable situation in the Shahrissabiz and Kitab districts). . According to the old tradition, the original Turks were called Navruz, the kingdom of the Subakh region of the ancient Turkic peoples, the last king of the Subakh region, who was a Turkic people.) was held in the vicinity of the castle.

Saeed Akram Khan is in the photo

Pictures taken in 1950 of the nephews of Pirimkul Ugli Nomir Palvan, Holman and Meili Baba.

In the photos, Abdurakhman, the grandson of Mustan, the brother of Nomir, and the wrestling hall he founded in the village of Nurafshan (ancient Chunaghar).

This is probably the saying in our country that "a horse will step on a horse's urn". He lived like a bird's sleep (1964-2012). During his short life, he was able to show his descendants like his grandfathers in the country by giving good deeds to the poor and giving good deeds to the captives. He was distinguished from his peers by his leadership and mentorship, he had many friends and students, among them were the champions of the world, his kindness to relatives and the young and old, to the poor, he did not spare the main part of the funds he earned from his struggles and his country, his name is proud of his friends and the old and the young. they remember In the national wrestling hall established by him, the children of his relatives are constantly receiving wrestling lessons from their coaches. If God is lucky, we are sure that among them will be young people who will wait for the flag of the country that will fulfill his dreams in the world wrestling arenas.

However, in the park, Mullah Achil Akhun, Mullah Eshmurad, Mullah Yormat and Hukim Bakhsh were glorifying Amir Olimkhan and Said Akromkhan by singing verses from epics. They were accompanied by gifts from Chirakchi, Chorjuy, Kulob, and Shahrisabz districts.

When the day reached the century, Tora Said Akrom Khan announced the end of the walk by clapping his hands. Shaikhislam Seyyid Shamonsurkhan first praised God, then his shadow on earth Amir Olimkhan and his grandson Said

Akromkhan, and prayed for peace, tranquility and blessings in the coming year. Saying amen to all, - he drew a blessing on his face. Seykhislam Shomansorkhan, who killed Mahmadvalikhan next to him, called Said Akromkhan to meet with Tora. Both of them went to the net. The sheikh introduced that person to the net. They looked at each other and asked for greetings on the tip of their tongues. That's why Churturmalik is more than happy. In 1916, when he demanded the property of the people and took men between the ages of 19 and 43 as laborers according to the decree of the Russian emperor Nicholas II, his cup of patience was full and the people revolted. Sayyid Yusuf Khan, one of the relatives of Mahmadvalikha, was one of the organizers of this rebellion. Bukhara commander Said Olimkhan's aide-de-camp Urganji calmed down the people who were in trouble, and Yusuf Khan fled to Kitab Bey Jo'rabek, went to Kokhan, served General Kaufman, and became a soldier.

Nowruz of 1920. In March, the weather changed and it was raining blessings. At the time when people's sparks of hope were emerging again, Vahobbek, originally from the large neighborhood of Chochurtma, brought wheat and rice to his villagers for Navroz feast. This was a help to feed the hungry people. When Davlatbergan Amin informed the messengers that there would be a large number of goats in the Shakarbulok caravanserai square near the lake in the morning, the messengers shouted about this event and ran through the park. the picture, you are looking at the images of the temple built in the style of the 8th century and preserved until now, and the landscape of the ancient caravanserai in front of the park.

When the Islamic caliphate came under the hands of the Abbasids in the eighth century, the Arabs gave great importance to Islamization in Movaranahur, especially in the Zarafshan and Kashqa oasis. they start appointing amirs and viceroys. In this way, a Parso emir with the title of Khujaboshi, a black-marked Parso from the descendants of Sulaiman, came to Subakh, and this old Kavchin, Chogurtma tribe, built an Islamic mosque, a house, and a shrine at the location of the temples of Iskifag, the religious center of Subakh, next to the Navruz playground. At dawn, people, young and old, on foot, on donkeys, on horseback, from all the villages of the region are coming to the village. From time to time, the horse and carriages of the rich are also seen. It was only then that it was seen that the messengers of the Torah worked in the Guzor bazaar shouting and shouting about this event. A race of people appeared in this ancient resort, and Navruz holiday was celebrated according to the tradition of its time. The

winners were determined by running, donkey, and horse races for teenage boys up to present-day Oligtepa (Subah).

In the photo, ancient Subah (Ulug Tepa)

Here is the one in the picture below, which brings our wonderful country Uzbekistan, including the family tree of New Uzbekistan, to the top in the world in terms of underground roads; it's like going down to the mysterious underground destination mentioned in the legends at the foot of the Sobak (O'lug) hill, which has a cultural heritage; The fact that it is said in the narrations that it is an urn with glazed and decorated earthenware, which is intended to enter the construction of an underground tunnel, also confirms our ideas above, i.e. it is dead.

There is a separate park for women and girls, and a trade market is organized on stalls in Kurgantepa (Sunaj) square. Kulob beg from the Bek quarter of the village, Murodbek's brother Rayim Toksaba, will conduct running races. The second judge of the race was Rakhimqul Toksoba from the Uzbek bell clan. In the meantime, Sayyid Akrom Khan and Shaykhulislam Seyyid

Shamonsur Khan, the imam of the mosque, Sayyid Qamaridin Khan and other scholars, who had read the morning prayer from Gulli Mosque, began to pray. People crowded around the picnic table, ate the food served by the servants, and began to go out to the theater and the park in turn. Teenagers, who have been taught to ride horses and donkeys since childhood, are gathering in separate villages and preparing for the race. Behind them are gathered teenagers running on foot. Carpets and felt blankets are spread around the arena, and the elders are sitting with their wrestlers from village to village. The audience is standing behind them.

On the sunny side of the field, there is a seat for the net, and on the right and left sides there is a place for officials. They are waiting for the tora in a row under the leadership of Mubinkhan, the son of the tora. Wrestlers from different regions of the region - Chorju, Chirakchi, Shahrisabz, Yakkabog, Denov, Sherabad, Kulob - are preparing for the fight. In the wrestling field, young children are fighting restlessly. The porters from Shahrisabz started the gallows. The clowns make the audience laugh with their antics. Elders of all the villages of the region, abjir, equestrian wrestlers, people from the village of Chugurtma, named after the seven mosques of Khoja Abulays, gathered according to ancient traditions. On the hill on the sunny side of the park, new brides, mothers leading

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